

Resilient Agri-food Supply Chains: Designing Cognitive User Interfaces with Hybrid Choice Models

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Abstract: Decision Support Systems (DSSs) for supply chains harness vast data to generate actionable insights, yet their effectiveness often falls short when users vary in age, digital literacy, and experience. These usability gaps become critical in volatile agrifood networks, where resilience hinges on the unpredictable nature of disruptions. Addressing this, our research introduces a human-centric Cognitive User Interface (CUI) framework tailored for DSSs operating under disruption. We employ Hybrid Choice Models (HCMs) to capture how diverse users trade off interface attributes such as update frequency, visualization detail, and adaptability when facing stochastic shocks. By integrating psychometric measures and socioeconomic covariates into the choice model, this framework proposes a method to quantify the impact of individual preferences on interface selections and features to adapt them to users. Ultimately, our framework advances resilient DSS design by uniting data-driven insights with adaptive, accessible interfaces that foster both user confidence and supply chain stability.

Keywords: Discrete Choice Models; System Design; Cognitive User Interface; Disruption; Industry 5.0

1. Introduction

Global supply chains' increasing complexity and volatility have made developing resilient systems a critical priority, especially within the agri-food sector (Zhong et al., 2024). Agri-food supply chains are particularly susceptible to disruptions due to their dependence on natural resources, which are often affected by climate change, geopolitical events, and market fluctuations (Stone & Rahimifard, 2018). These disruptions can significantly impact the efficiency and effectiveness of supply chain operations, leading to increased costs, reduced product quality, and potential food shortages (Zhong et al., 2024).

In this context, Decision Support Systems (DSSs) have emerged as essential tools for enhancing supply chain resilience. However, the effectiveness of these systems is contingent upon their usability and accessibility, which can be influenced by user characteristics such as age, digital literacy, and working experience (Hamou et al., 2023; Fayoumi et al., 2018). Moreover, the role of the unobservable psychological factors (i.e., latent variables), that impact user behaviour, preferences, and interaction with DSSs is largely overlooked in designing the interface between users and the DSSs. For instance, the user's perception of disruption can affect how users interact with a system and their preference for certain interface features in the context of DSS responsible for resilience in supply chain management. This gap in understanding and measuring latent variables presents a significant challenge in developing user-centered and resilient DSSs for agri-food supply chains.

To address this challenge, recent research has begun to explore the integration of Cognitive User Interfaces

(CUIs) within DSSs. CUIs are designed to adapt to user preferences and cognitive styles, thereby enhancing the usability and accessibility of information (Gou et al., 2024; Young, 2010). This approach aligns with the broader trend towards human-centric design in supply chain management within the framework of Industry 5.0, which emphasizes the centrality of understanding and accommodating user needs (Cotta et al., 2023). The goal of this work is to propose a methodology for designing CUIs for DSSs, considering disruptions, focusing on the agri-food supply chain. This research aims to integrate Hybrid Choice Models (HCMs) to account for both observable and latent variables, thereby enhancing the resilience and usability of DSSs.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a literature review of the topic. Section 3 explains the power and relevance of HCM from a theoretical perspective. Section 4 outlines the methodology of the proposed framework. Section 5 presents the preliminary results and the implications of the findings. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper by summarizing the research contributions, limitations, and future research directions.

2. Literature Review

Recent work has developed DSS tools to improve supply-chain resilience, especially in agri-food. Many approaches use simulation and optimization to model disruptions. For example, Tsiamas et al. (2021) present a simulation-based DSS that mitigates climate-related disruptions in a dairy manufacturing supply chain. Similarly, Clavijo-Burítica et al. (2023) combine mathematical programming with

simulation to design resilient agri-food networks (a Colombian coffee case) that “measure, predict, compare, and improve” resilience metrics. Other studies apply multi-criteria methods (PROMETHEE, AHP, etc.) to supplier selection with resilience criteria. These works focus on technical resilience (availability, connectivity, risk mitigation) but largely omit human factors, how users interact with such systems, and, in particular, how a manager’s perception of disruption or cognitive state affects system use (Aungkulanon et al., 2024).

Brunner et al. (2017) report that applying user-centred design practices consistently improves the perceived utility and safety of clinical DSS. Fayoumi et al. (2018) similarly stress designing CDSS interfaces to “reduce cognitive burden and information overload”, making them more intuitive for busy clinicians. Likewise, Chen et al. (2023) emphasize that DSS developers must account for user characteristics: they argue that designers “need to understand the user’s concept of interaction and the degree of mastering the computer” so that the interface “automatically adjusts and guides users to better conduct decision-making”. This aligns with a broader Industry 5.0 trend toward human-centric supply chains, where DSS must serve diverse users (with varying digital skills, stress levels, etc.). In short, interface research is moving from one-size-fits-all GUIs to adaptable UIs that consider user context, accessibility needs, and even affective or stress factors.

2.1 Cognitive User Interfaces in Decision-Making

Alongside user-centred design, CUIs have emerged as a paradigm in Human-machine Interface for decision support. They go beyond static menus by embedding intelligence into the UI. Young (2010) defines cognitive UIs as interfaces that can “support inference and reasoning, planning under uncertainty, short-term adaptation, and long-term learning from experience”. In practice, CUIs often take the form of conversational agents, adaptive visualization dashboards, or context-aware assistants. For example, He et al. (2021) design a chatbot to serve as a CUI for financial portfolio DSS; users interact in natural language as if with a human advisor, yielding “an easy-to-use interface” for complex optimization tasks. In sum, CUIs aim to enhance human-computer interaction by adapting to human cognitive strategies, supporting reasoning and learning, and using AI (e.g. Bayesian or reinforcement methods) to manage uncertainty.

2.2 Discrete and Hybrid Choice Models in Interface-DSS Research

DCMs have recently begun to appear in interface research to let designers quantify user preferences over UI features. For example, Seneler et al. (2009) used a conjoint DCM experiment to rank five interface design attributes (customization, adaptivity, memory load, content density, speed). They found that “speed is the most important and customization is the least important feature” in driving user preference. These part-worth findings helped guide UI prototyping for adaptive systems. Qi et al. (2020)

similarly applied DCM to mobile payment interfaces: analyzing ~270 respondents, they discovered that security and convenience dominated preferences over entertainment or aesthetic aspects. They note that these choice patterns “reflect consumer psychology” and can inform design for specific user groups.

However, DCMs assume all relevant factors are observed and do not consider how latent variables, such as psychological factors, can affect stakeholders’ preferences. While HCM can be used to integrate both observable and unobservable variables into choice models (Zhang et al., 2025), overcoming the DCMs limitations, to the best of our knowledge, no published work has yet used HCM to tailor DSS interfaces based on users’ latent perceptions. To this extent, the literature has: (a) developed DSS methods for resilience (Tsiamas et al., 2021; Clavijo-Buritica et al., 2023); (b) shifted UI design toward user-centric, adaptive, cognitively aware interfaces (Chen et al. 2023); and (c) applied stated-preference models to rank UI features (Qi et al. 2020).

This paper addresses that gap by proposing a HCM-based approach to model how a decision maker’s latent disruption perception (and related attitudes) affect interface preferences in resilient agri-food DSS.

3.Theoretical Background

In the context of user behavior analysis, latent variables represent psychological constructs such as attitudes, perceptions, habits, or emotions that cannot be directly measured but exert systematic influence on observable behaviors.

Zhang et al. (2025) applied an HCM to study the effect of food neophobia (treated as a latent variable) on the willingness to consume functional rice, demonstrating the model’s utility in capturing psychological factors affecting choice behaviour. Similarly, in the context of supply chain, the perception of disruption (PD) can be considered as a latent variable affecting users’ preferences towards different interface settings. It represents a key psychological construct that influences how users interact with DSSs. This latent variable captures the subjective assessment of instability, uncertainty, or interruption within the decision-making environment.

The perception of disruption may manifest in several dimensions:

- **Threat assessment:** The degree to which a user perceives disruptions as threatening to organizational objectives.
- **Control perception:** The extent to which users believe they can influence outcomes during disruptive events.
- **Information processing under uncertainty:** How users evaluate and integrate information when faced with incomplete or rapidly changing data.

- **Temporal orientation:** Whether users focus on immediate responses or long-term adaptation strategies.

Several factors may influence the perception of disruption, including professional experience, role in organization, digital literacy, age, and educational background. By incorporating the perception of disruption as a latent variable in our HCM framework, we can better account for the psychological aspects of user interaction with decision support systems under uncertainty.

4. Methodological Framework

The objective of this study is to propose a methodological framework to support the design of CUIs for DSSs in disruptive environments. The key components of the proposed approach are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: IDEF0 framework for CUI design

The framework takes several key inputs to guide the definition of observable and latent variables (detailed in sections 4.1 and 4.2). These inputs include GUI characteristics expressed as attributes and their corresponding levels, along with relevant psychometric indicators. Three critical factors control this design process: perception of disruptions, user characteristics, and user preferences.

The framework then employs the Human-Computer Model as a mechanism to derive user preferences for different interface configurations (discussed in section 4.3). This process generates three primary outputs: the final CUI design, user clusters based on preferences and psychometric-socioeconomic factors, and valuable insights into how users perceive disruptions.

4.1 Observable variables specification

Observable variables can be directly quantified and assessed through interviews or surveys. In the context of the study, the first stage involves the definition of the design space over which users express preferences. This requires a structured process that includes:

- **Identification of relevant attributes:** It refers to interface features and settings (e.g., interaction and visualization mode) that can be selected

through literature review, expert consultation, or empirical observations.

- **Specification of attribute levels:** For each attribute, a finite set of levels is defined to construct realistic design alternatives. It means defining specifications for each attribute identified (e.g., speech, gesture, etc.).

These elements represent one of the inputs of the model, on which the user can express preferences through the state choice experiment. Additional observable variables are represented by demographics and socioeconomic factors that can affect the user's choice.

4.2 Incorporating latent variables through HCM

The perception of disruption refers to the user's internal assessment of instability, uncertainty, or interruption within a digital decision-making environment. This perception is expected to influence the desirability of interface features that convey robustness, clarity, or adaptability.

It can be captured indirectly through psychometric indicators, measured through Likert scales, assessing what is the user's perception of disruption by proposing simple questions to rate. The estimation process involves two interlinked components: a measurement model, which maps psychometric indicators to the latent variable, and a structural model, which links both observable and latent variables to the stated user choices (Zhang et al., 2025).

4.3 Model Estimation and Use

The last phase of applying the choice model involves the data collection phase and the model estimation.

4.3.1 Data collection

Data collection can be held through surveys, interviews, focus groups, and more. Interviewees and potential final users are asked to, first of all, fill in data about their demographics and socio-economic factors, and rate the psychometric indicators.

After that, a key part is played by the Stated Choice Experiment. It presents participants with a series of hypothetical but realistic decision scenarios on CUI designs and asks them to choose their preferred option in each scenario. Each alternative is defined by a specific combination of design attributes. To reduce the complexity of the full factorial design, a fraction of possible combinations is considered. While random selection can be an approach, it can lead to poor model estimation. Alternative approaches, such as orthogonal, efficient, and optimal designs, offer better estimation and minimal standard errors by carefully selecting choice sets based on prior information (JM Rose and MCJ Bliemer, 2008).

4.3.1 Model estimation tools

To estimate the model, various specialized software tools have been developed. For instance, Apollo (Hess and Palma, 2019), an R package designed for flexible and high-performance estimation of choice models, has been

successfully employed in behavioral transport studies to estimate both traditional and hybrid models. Similarly, Biogeme (Bierlaire, 2020) is used to estimate the models’ parameters using maximum likelihood estimation.

4.4 CUI Evaluation metrics

After the model parameters have been estimated, interviewees’ preferences can be derived and used to design the CUI. Nonetheless, involving users in a final evaluation round becomes essential to further verify the effectiveness of such interfaces. Among them, usability (Leroy et al., 2020), perceived ease of use, usefulness, and intuitiveness (Cheng & Senathirajah, 2023), acceptability and satisfaction (Chateau, Benjamin et al., 2020; Leroy et al., 2020), and more can be considered.

5. Results & Discussion

5.1. CERERE Case Study

This study draws upon the CERERE (CEreals REsiliency REvolution for Agile Supply Chain Management in the Mediterranean) project, which investigates advanced methodologies and technologies aimed at enhancing decision-making capabilities among agri-food supply chain stakeholders in the context of systemic disruptions. A central challenge is the heterogeneity of end-users, which significantly impacts the usability of such smart systems. This diversity necessitates the development of adaptive, user-centered interfaces that ensure equitable access to actionable insights and foster inclusive decision-making across the supply chain ecosystem.

5.2 Definition of the latent variable

As previously introduced, PD is conceptualized as a latent psychological variable reflecting the degree to which users feel that external disruptions (e.g., geopolitical shocks, market volatility, climate events) impact their digital decision-making environment. Since PD is not directly observable, it must be inferred from indirect measures.

Psychometric factors: PD is best conceptualized through targeted psychometric items designed to capture, for instance, cognitive stress, control, adaptability, and awareness under disruptive conditions. These items will be included in the user questionnaire, and a Likert-scale can be used by interviewees to rate them. Finally, results can be analyzed using measurement models.

Socio-economic factors: To account for individual heterogeneity and explain variability in PD, a selection of socio-economic characteristics will be included in the latent variable model. These variables serve to explain PD and will be used to estimate model parameters. Table 1 shows a list of potential factors to be considered.

Table 1: Socio-economic factors

Factor	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Age	<20	20<A<40	≥40
Professional role	Operator	Administrative	Director

Years of experience	>5	5>E>10	≥10
Frequency of past exposure	12 Months	1 Year	>1 Year
Yearly income	<30k	30k<I<50k	≥50k
Educational background	Elementary	High-school	University
Digital literacy level	None	Enough good	Excellent

5.3 Definition of alternatives and attributes

To model users’ preferences for CUIs in disrupted agri-food supply chain contexts, we define a choice set composed of alternative interface configurations. Each alternative is described as a unique combination of design attributes, which represent key dimensions of the user experience relevant to resilience, accessibility, and adaptability under uncertainty.

Below, each attribute and its corresponding levels are described, and finally summarized in Table 2, along with the reasoning behind its inclusion.

Table 2: Interface attributes and levels

Attribute	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Interaction	Static	Dynamic	
Visualization	Text	Numerical	Graphical
Level of Detail	Synthetic	Detailed	Customized
Update Rate	Real time	Periodic	On demand
Adaptability	Yes	No	
Alerts	Visual pop-up	Audio	None

Interaction Mode: Either static or dynamic modes can be considered. The first generates interfaces where content does not update dynamically or respond to user inputs in real time, which are easier to implement but less adaptive to fast-changing conditions. Dynamic features make interfaces adjustable to user input or external changes. More engaging and responsive, particularly relevant in disrupted contexts where information may shift rapidly.

Visualization Type: The type of information visualization provided to users can be: plain written form, which prioritizes clarity and accessibility for low-digital-literacy users; quantitative data such as tables or numerical analyses, suitable for users accustomed to structured decision-making formats; graphical output, such as charts, icons, and data visualizations, which facilitates rapid comprehension and pattern recognition, especially under cognitive load.

Level of Detail: The information and data can be shown with different levels of detail: high-level summaries or key

indicators support fast decision-making and reduce complexity; in-depth views of data, including disaggregated components, can be useful for expert users or decisions requiring nuanced analysis; customized solutions allow users to switch between levels of detail depending on the specific activity carried out and on the level of expertise.

Update Rate: Information can be updated in real-time, at periodic intervals, or on demand. In the first case, information is continuously updated. This is vital during disruptions where timely information is critical. On the other hand, on-demand requests are made manually by users, which reduces data load but increases the risk of missing important updates on the current system status.

Adaptability: The interface can be adjusted based on user profile, behavior, or context (e.g., language preference, past usage patterns) or can remain uniform for all users, which is easier to develop and maintain but less inclusive in diverse user populations. Its usefulness can be evaluated as well by stakeholders.

Alerts and Notifications: These can be displayed through visual pop-up, with on-screen alerts, audio-sound cues or voice alerts, useful for hands-free contexts or users with visual impairments. Eventually, no alert mechanism can be selected, reducing the cognitive distraction but may delay user response to critical changes.

6. Conclusions

In this paper, we have introduced a novel methodological framework that integrates HCMs to design CUIs for DSS in disrupted agri-food supply chains. By embedding the unobservable latent construct “perception of disruption” within our choice model, we aim to quantify how users’ subjective assessments of supply-chain instability systematically shape preferences over interface features. This approach advances the state of the art by moving beyond purely observable UI attributes and enables a richer, psychologically informed analysis of human-computer interaction under uncertainty.

On a practical standpoint, our framework offers practitioners a systematic tool for building human-centric, resilience-oriented GUIs: (1) it identifies which design attributes best mitigate users’ perceived disruption stress; (2) it enables the derivation of user clusters based on both observable characteristics and latent perceptions, so that interfaces can be tailored to distinct stakeholder groups (e.g., farmers vs. retailers); and (3) it surfaces the critical role of real-time updates and simplified visualizations when disruption perception is high. Academically, our contribution lies in the formal integration of latent psychological factors into CUI design, bridging cognitive engineering theory with discrete-choice econometrics in the context of Industry 5.0’s human-centric vision.

Despite these advances, our study has limitations. Data collection relies on stated-choice experiments and self-reported psychometric scales, which may introduce hypothetical bias and measurement error. Future work

should validate these findings through field deployments and by incorporating observed interaction logs. Moreover, our current model considers a single latent variable (perception of disruption); additional constructs, such as risk propensity or trust in automation, could further enrich interface personalization. Finally, exploring dynamic, sequential choice models would allow CUIs to adapt over time as users’ perceptions evolve during prolonged disruptions. These extensions will deepen our understanding of resilient, human-centered DSS design in agri-food and beyond.

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